

TRAINING TEACHERS OF PRE-UNIVERSITY LEVEL IN ABSTRACTION AS SKILL OF COMPUTATIONAL THINKING

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Abstract

Purpose – Several studies carried out in recent years confirm the importance of introducing Computational Thinking and Programming as cross-curricular competences, not only in university studies but, above all, among Secondary School students.

Methodology/approach - We have developed a project for Primary and Secondary Education teachers in different areas in the Basque Country to promote the acquisition of Abstraction.

Findings – This article presents the results of the work carried out in the 2018-2019, 2019-2020 and 2020-2021 academic years, where computational thinking, and abstraction particularly, can be a cross-curricular competence for any field: engineering, management, economics, etc.

Research limitations/implications – We have developed a project for Primary and Secondary Education teachers in different areas in the Basque Country to promote the acquisition of Abstraction.

Practical implications – Incorporating computational thinking into the educational curriculum can benefit students, in any field and at any age.

Key words: abstraction, computational thinking, cross-curricular competence.

Introduction

To be successful in the changing world we live in, one needs to be adaptable, responsive to change, able to solve problems and develop software and hardware, or even use and generate technology. According to Sá and Serpa (2018) and considering the current reconfiguration of Higher Education in Europe, its vision and mission and its constant search to provide its students with the knowledge and competences that will enable them to succeed in their future professional life, Higher Education institutions are obliged to provide their students with a strong technical and scientific background.

Contrary to popular belief, CT is not only applicable in the field of computer science or robotics. Learning to think computationally, starting with learning to use abstraction as a basic tool for reasoning, brings with it a number of educational benefits that strengthen intellectual skills and enhance learning in any subject.

Jeanette Wing (2006) was who gave the definition of CT that is considered most popular: “Computational Thinking is the thought processes involved in formulating problems and their

solutions so that the solutions are represented in a form that can be effectively carried out by an information-processing agent”.

We are not only talking about big problems solved by researchers, innovation or technology development, we are also talking about thinking in such a way that, when we solve problems, we can rely, if we need or want to, on technology, on digital tools. Let us think, for example, of the kitchen robot, which can help us to improve the quality of life or, in general, all those devices that help us to be more efficient in the work we do. Let us think about the future work that we will develop taking into account the technological advances that are available to us at that time (Geppert et al., 2017).

In the Autonomous Community of the Basque Country, the Basque Government's Department of Education, in the HEZIBERRI 2020 plan (Basque Government, 2014), which is a plan for future education, includes digital competence among the basic cross-curricular or generic competences. Likewise, in order to train non-university teachers in CT, with the aim of enabling them to implement it in their classrooms, it promotes training courses within the called PrestGara programme (Basque Government, 2019).

This article analyses an experience carried out in the courses given in the period 2018-2021 within the PrestGara programme, with the participation of Primary, Secondary and High School teachers.

Abstraction and Computer Science

Computational Thinking (CT), as a cross-curricular competence, has several concepts in common with some innovative methodologies, such as PBL (Problem Based Learning), and is closely related to some fields, such as STEM. Concepts such as “knowledge construction” are included in the DNA of CT, but it does not imply that it is a property of CT. We mean that there are some relationships between Computational Thinking and some innovative methodologies. According to Jonassen and Gram-Hansen (2019), CT and PBL search and increase processes as problem-solving, problem understanding and critical thinking. In the same way, Chen (2017) focused on the advantages of these methodologies for the programming language teaching. The connection between CT and PBL is also cited by Gao et al. (2019), relating the problem-solving process when it is divided into several steps to analyze problems and establishing logic thinking.

According to the Computer Science Teachers Association (CSTA) and the International Society for Technology in Education (ISTE) (2011), the main characteristics of CT include:

- Logically analysing and organising data.
- Data modelling, data abstractions and simulations.
- Formulating problems in such a way that computers can help.
- Identifying, testing and implementing possible solutions.
- Automating solutions through algorithmic thinking.
- Generalising and applying this process to other problems.

Thus, according to Liu and Wang (2010), Computational Thinking is a hybrid of other modes of thinking, such as abstract thinking, logical thinking, modelling thinking and constructive thinking.

We believe that these concepts and skills are part of Computational Thinking, but it will be better defined, and therefore easier, more accurate and appropriate to assess, if we use the right sequence of skills.

Therefore, we can define Computational Thinking as a type of analytical thinking that employs mathematical and engineering thinking to understand and solve complex problems within the constraints of the real world through an appropriate use of its skills. (Bilbao, Bravo, García, Varela, & Rebollar, 2017). The skills that we consider to be part of CT are the following: abstraction; modelling; decomposition; algorithmic thinking and automation; data collection, analysis and representation; generalisation; evaluation and adjustment.

In addition, the most important and highest level thinking process in Computational Thinking is that of abstraction (Wing, 2011).

Since abstraction is considered a key CT skill, some authors think that the introduction of this cross-curricular competence and programming in primary education requires empirical research at the earliest age at which students can handle abstraction (Armoni & Gal-Ezer, 2014).

The different ways of seeing abstraction are closely related to the field of Computer Science and can be very useful when we want to apply abstraction in exercises or programmes in this field. Nevertheless, they are not two different forms of abstraction, but different ways of understanding or applying abstraction, and there are other ways of seeing it for other fields such as Art, Medicine, etc.

How to train in abstraction

A training experience carried out in the period 2018-2021 is presented. During this period, training courses were given to Primary, Secondary and High School teachers in the Basque Country as part of the “PrestGara” programme. These training courses aim to show teachers the different CT skills, so that they can subsequently put these concepts into practice in their subjects. The ultimate goal of the entire process is for students from primary to secondary school to become familiar with skills such as abstraction through various activities. In this way, by the end of their school studies, and before entering university, they will have acquired the CT competence that is so important for tackling the problems they will face both in their university degrees and in their subsequent professional development.

3.1. Structure of the course

The course had an initial session in which the theoretical contents to be addressed, the study materials to be used and the development of the tasks to be carried out during the weeks of the course have been explained. The work that must be handed in periodically is tutored and it receives the corresponding feedback from the teaching staff. In these assignments, course attendees prepare exercises for their students in primary and secondary classes to practice and reinforce their skills, particularly abstraction. These tasks, developed and presented by course attendees, are evaluated by the course teaching team and represent the grade that these participants obtain as a result of their progress in the course.

Both at the beginning and at the end of the course, participants have to answer two surveys. The first one measures the degree of prior knowledge they have about CT, and the second one measures the degree of satisfaction with which they finish the course.

3.2. Description

The courses have been approached from a practical point of view, but providing the participants with the essential theoretical notions. Thus, the first session begins with the introduction of the basic fundamentals of Computational Thinking, defined as the set of thinking processes involved in the formulation of problems and representation of their solutions, so that these

solutions can be executed by an information processing agent (human, computers or combinations of both). CT is a cognitive competence that includes the mental tools needed to solve complex problems, and it includes the process skill that allows to have the problem perfectly focused and understood, as well as the possible ways of solving it in order to subsequently use the digital tools. It is explained that all this is possible based on the skills that make up and characterise this competence: abstraction; modelling; decomposition; algorithmic thinking and automation; data collection, analysis and representation; generalisation; evaluation and adjustment. Its direct relationship with STEAM is also established. Subsequently, emphasis is placed on the need to create activities that can be used in the classroom to effectively develop this competence.

In addition to introducing the theoretical idea of CT competence, we can distinguish several other objectives in the taught courses. A first objective is to explain by means of examples each of the skills of this competence, with special emphasis on Abstraction, which is the essence of CT. This part includes the design of the assessment rubric for these skills, as will be seen later.

A second objective has been to explain how to design activities aimed at developing the CT competence, which can be used in the subjects taught by each teacher. The aim of these activities is for students to acquire CT skills, so that the level of acquisition of this competence can be assessed at the same time as the knowledge of the subject itself.

It has been detected that it is important to be clear about the ultimate goal of the activity. We must not lose sight of the fact that the final aim is for teachers to integrate this problem-solving competence into their classes. On the one hand, these activities should serve as support for the learning of the different subjects and, on the other, for the student to acquire CT skills.

3.3. Development of the training

The courses were divided into three parts. The first part dealt with the basic concepts of CT, developing two types of examples. On the one hand, those that served to illustrate a specific CT skill and, on the other hand, examples of activities that, suitably structured, served to show the use of CT through the set of skills that make it up. This part also included the design of the evaluation rubric. In the second part, students carried out their own examples and activities as practice in applying the concepts explained. This part was tutored, and consisted of the production and delivery of several documents, which finally made up the activity that each course participant had to prepare to put into practice with their students. The third part was a final session in which the participants presented their work.

Once the concept of abstraction has been explained, a tool has been provided to participants in order to evaluate the level of acquisition of this skill by their students through the tasks proposed to them. For this purpose, the rubric shown in Table 1 has been proposed in the course. It is a simple and quick method for assessment, and at the same time, it can be applied in various fields, without being anchored to the specifics of the subject or problem.

Table 1. Abstraction assessment rubric

Poor (0)	Student does not identify any of the main objectives or ideas of the problem to be solved. Student does not eliminate any of the unnecessary details of the problem to be solved.
Not-enough (1)	Student does not identify any of the main objectives or ideas of the problem to be solved. Student eliminates some of the unnecessary details of the problem to be solved.
Fair (2)	Student identifies some of the main objectives or ideas of the problem to be solved. Student eliminates some of the unnecessary details of the problem to be solved.
Advanced (3)	Student identifies the main objectives or ideas of the problem to be solved. Student eliminates all the unnecessary details of the problem to be solved.
Excellent (4)	Student identifies the main objectives or ideas of the problem, and expresses them correctly. Student eliminates all the unnecessary details of the problem to be solved.

The levels of acquisition of abstraction will be determined by the percentage of objectives and main ideas of the problem that are identified, as well as the percentage of unnecessary details that are removed. Remember, as McGregor (2006) says, that abstraction removes details from a view of the system but not from the system. This implies that details are virtually eliminated to get to that main idea, but then they have to be worked with to solve the problem.

Assessment and discussion

Information was collected from the participants (pre-university teachers) at the beginning of the course through a survey divided into three sections: information about the participant, whether they had knowledge of CT prior to the course, and the motivation for participating in the course.

With regard to the most descriptive part, 64.5% of the teaching staff who took part in the courses were women, and the majority of them taught mainly in Secondary Education and High School (95%), while the rest taught or had taught in Vocational Training or Primary Education.

With regard to the subjects taught by the participants in their centres, practically all subjects taught in Secondary and High School are covered, as can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Subjects taught by participants

Mathematics	Biology	Spanish language	Basque language
Physics /Chemistry	Applied Anatomy	Entrepreneurship	English language
Informatics	Earth Sciences	Economics	ICT
Technology	Contemporary World Sciences	Scientific Culture	Social Sciences
Plastic	Geology	Ethics	

As it can be seen, there are subjects corresponding to all fields of education, from the most technological to those corresponding to the Humanities. This is important, as Computational Thinking, and particularly abstraction skill, can be a cross-curricular for any area, although it obviously has a greater direct application in STEM fields.

At the beginning of the course, all teachers expressed their lack of knowledge about CT. Most of the participants asked before the course what Computational Thinking was. A question that was also common before the start of the course was whether CT was exclusively aimed at programming topics.

As for the main reasons for attending the course, they were as follows:

- Use of new ways of teaching in order to attract students' attention.
- The need for teachers and their teaching methods to adapt to the near future.
- Providing students with cross-curricular competences, which are of interest for both their personal and professional life.
- Encourage students to understand computer programmes, for example, Scratch.

At the end of the courses, participants have to fill in a final evaluation survey with a 5-point Likert scale, where the scores are “1 = Strongly disagree” and “5 = Strongly agree”.

Table 3 shows the questions as well as the descriptive statistics: mean, standard deviation, skewness coefficient and kurtosis.

It can be seen that all the questions are rated above 3 (in fact, almost all above 4), and that they are asymmetrical distributions with the left tail of the distribution longer than the right as all the asymmetry coefficients are negative. Statistics indicate a good assessment by the participants, who, it should be remembered, had started with a null or almost null level of CT.

Positive kurtosis coefficients indicate that the corresponding distributions have higher skewness than the Normal distribution; conversely, negative skewness coefficients indicate that the corresponding distributions are flatter than the Normal distribution. A distribution with a positive kurtosis value indicates that the distribution has heavier tails than the normal distribution, and in the case of the question “The given material has helped me to develop the course”, the kurtosis value is higher than 3.5. This item also has the highest mean. This leads us to think that the examples given during the course, in addition to the rest of the material, are successful in introducing CT to teachers who did not know what it was and in any field of education.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics for the final assessment questions

	Mean	Std. Dev.	Skew.	Kurt.
The face-to-face classes have been necessary to understand CT.	4,26	,999	-1,634	2,854
The activities presented in the classes have been adequate for the purpose of the course.	4,00	1,095	-,976	,408
The activities explained have had the appropriate level.	4,10	1,106	-1,150	,696
The given material has helped me to develop the course.	4,29	,938	-1,673	3,645
Planning online activities has helped me understand CT.	4,16	,934	-,865	-,138
The estimated time to make the deliveries has been adequate.	4,10	1,044	-1,331	1,595
The feedback received has been helpful in solving the doubts.	3,87	1,258	-1,030	,016
The course has met my expectations.	3,84	1,214	-,627	-,740

Finally, the assignments submitted by the course participants were also evaluated. These assignments, designed and developed by the course participants themselves, presented activities to be carried out in their primary and secondary classes to strengthen the concepts and skills related to Computational Thinking. The objective is, on the one hand, to practice and carry out the inclusion of CT in their classrooms, and on the other hand, to measure the understanding and progress of the participants.

The evaluation was carried out by means of two grades:

- Participation grade.
- Progress grade.

The participation grade indicates in some way the participant's interest in learning the concepts presented throughout the course, valuing the questions and answers in discussion forums, the response to small follow-up tests, and the “participation” itself with the delivery of the work requested throughout the course.

The progress grade values the quality of the assignments that they, the participants, present as activities of the course and the final work that they present, in which they put into practice all the knowledge acquired throughout the course, designing exercises or tasks to be implemented in their classrooms in order to apply concepts like Abstraction. The correction of these works made by the participants themselves based on the feedback provided by the course teachers is also taken into account.

If we compare the grades obtained by the participants by intervals (Fig. 1), we see this difference between the participation grade and the progress grade. The implementation of concepts such as abstraction in the tasks of the subjects, in the day-to-day life of the schools, is a complicated aspect that is helped by the feedback provided during the course.

Fig. 1. Comparison of participation and progress grades by intervals.

Conclusion

Training in Computational Thinking, in general, and in the concept of Abstraction, in particular, is a current challenge in the educational systems of many countries. This training at the student level must begin in pre-university education, and to this end, Primary and Secondary school teachers must be trained to be able to apply and implement these concepts in their classes.

According to the teachers participating in the course, which has been running for three years, Abstraction is one of the most difficult Computational Thinking skills to understand without training support. However, after the training, it is possible to transfer it to pre-university classes. Moreover, this translation can be carried out in any field of Education.

It is important to highlight the heterogeneity of the teachers who want to train in Computational Thinking, coming from subjects as disparate in the education system as Computer Science and Art. In our opinion, this shows, on the one hand, the cross-cutting component of CT and its validity, and on the other, its interest for pre-university teachers. Thus, CT should be a cross-curricular competence throughout the whole education system.

Finally, we cannot forget the evaluative part, without which any educational process would not be complete. A rubric has been proposed to measure abstraction in the exercises that a teacher has to assess. This rubric is general, as it is the concept of Abstraction, and can be applied to any type of exercise. But like Abstraction itself, which has different nuances depending on where it is applied, the rubric needs to be “adapted”, as shown in the previous sections, to the exercises to be assessed.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the grant GIU21/043 of the University of the Basque Country. We are also grateful to the Basque Government, who supports the “PrestGara” programme. Finally, our thanks to all the international Bebras community for its huge effort to promote Computational Thinking among school students at all ages..

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